

Climate suitability technical report of *Citripestis sagittiferella*

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[Citripestis_sagittiferella _ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf](#)

The file contains the description of the methodology and results of the systematic literature search and climate suitability assessment for *Citripestis sagittiferella*. The results of the databases interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. The methodology of the climate suitability analysis is also explained, although we refer to the related PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health et al., 2023) for an exhaustive and more comprehensive discussion of the results.

[Citripestis_sagittiferella _ANNEX_A_Master_file.xlsx](#)

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields is in [Citripestis_sagittiferella _ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf](#).

[Citripestis_sagittiferella _ANNEX_B_Observations.csv](#)

The file contains the list of the organism observed distribution at a global level. Both point locations and administrative units are included.

[Citripestis_sagittiferella _Observations.jpg](#)

The map contains the observed distribution of *Citripestis sagittiferella*.

[Citripestis_sagittiferella _PRA.gpkg](#)

This is a GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors and managers to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest (IPPC, 2013). This analysis is typically based on pest biology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available (Devorshak, 2012). An extensive literature research, in accordance with EFSA systematic review methodology (EFSA, 2010), was performed to gather relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *C. sagittiferella*. The data extracted from the literature search were used to analyse the climate suitability of *C. sagittiferella* in the EU.

Note on this report

This document includes a description of the climate suitability analysis methodology applied to *Citripestis sagittiferella*. The analysis was conducted in the context of the *EFSA Pest risk assessment of Citripestis sagittiferella for the European Union* (EFSA Panel on Plant Health et al., 2023). For a complete description and discussion of the results of the present analysis, inserted in the framework of a pest risk assessment, please refer to the related PRA.

Methods

Systematic literature review

Searches were performed to identify relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *C. sagittiferella*. Table 1 shows the list of databases that were consulted. Results from the scientific databases were crosschecked and integrated (if needed) with records of the EPPO Global database¹ and CABI².

Table 1: List of databases consulted for the extensive literature search

Databases	Platforms
Web of Science Core Collection	Web of Science
Biosis	
CAB Abstracts	
Chinese Science Citation Database	
Current Content Connect	
FSTA- the food science resource	
Korean Journal Database	
Medline	
Russian Science Citation Index	
SciELO Citation Index	
Scopus	Scopus

A combination of the scientific and international common names of the pest, retrieved from EPPO, CABI, and CABI Thesaurus³ (shown in Table 2), was used to interrogate the bibliographic databases. No other keywords were used (e.g., “biology”, “physiology”, “temperature”, etc...) not to limit the retrieval of documents that could include information useful for the purposes of this search as secondary information, especially in the case of pest distribution.

¹ <https://gd.eppo.int/>

² <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/>

³ <https://www.cabi.org/publishing-products/cab-thesaurus/>

Table 2: Taxonomy, EPPO Code and main hosts of *Citripestis sagittiferella*.

Scientific name	<i>Citripestis sagittiferella</i> (Moore)
Other scientific names	<i>Nephoptyx sagittiferella</i> (Moore) <i>Mussidia pectinicornella</i> (Hampson)* <i>Citripestis pectinicornella</i> *
International common names	Citrus fruit borer, lemon fruit borer, parkia pod borer, citrus pulp borer
Taxonomy	Kingdom: <i>Animalia</i> Phylum: <i>Arthropoda</i> Class: <i>Insecta</i> Order: <i>Lepidoptera</i> Family: <i>Pyralidae</i>
EPPO Code	CITPSA
Crop hosts	Canavalia gladiata, Cassia fistula, Citrus, Citrus aurantiifolia, Citrus aurantium, Citrus hystrix, Citrus limon, Citrus maxima, Citrus medica, Citrus reticulata, Citrus sinensis, Citrus x paradisi

*Uncertain name

Table 3 shows the query syntax used in Web of Science and Scopus platforms, the date of the search, and the number of documents obtained.

Table 3: Research strings used for the bibliographic databases consulted

Platform	Set	Date of search	Query	Results
Web of Science	#1	16/06/2022	TS=(<i>"Citripestis sagittiferella"</i> OR <i>"Nephoptyx sagittiferella"</i> OR <i>"Mussidia pectinicornella"</i> OR <i>"Citripestis pectinicornella"</i> OR <i>"citrus fruit borer"</i> OR <i>"lemon fruit borer"</i> OR <i>"parkia pod borer"</i> OR <i>"citrus pulp borer"</i>)All Databases excluding Data citation Index and Zoological Report	32
SCOPUS	#1	16/06/2022	TITLE-ABS-KEY(<i>"Citripestis sagittiferella"</i> OR <i>"Nephoptyx sagittiferella"</i> OR <i>"Mussidia pectinicornella"</i> OR <i>"Citripestis pectinicornella"</i> OR <i>"citrus fruit borer"</i> OR <i>"lemon fruit borer"</i> OR <i>"parkia pod borer"</i> OR <i>"citrus pulp borer"</i>)	8

All the references were exported to the reference manager software EndoNoteX9 (The EndNote Team, 2013) and checked for duplicates. The remaining references were then imported (as a compressed Endnote library) in the software DistillerSR (Evidence Partners, 2021) and screened.

Document screening

Document screening followed a two-step approach. In both steps the documents were screened answering the question *"Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?"*.

The first step was based on titles and abstracts. It was applied to identify the presence of elements indicating the potential availability of information on physiology, ecology, and distribution of the pest in the full text. In case of positive answer, the type of information potentially available was specified (i.e., Physiology/Ecology, Distribution, or Other) (see Figure 1 as an example).

Reference Details

RefID: 1, Pest categorisation of *Citripestis sagittiferella*
 Bragard, Claude, Dehnen-Schmutz, Katharina Di Serio, Francesco Gonthier, Paolo Jacques, Marie-Agnes Jaques Miret, Josep Anton Justesen, Annemarie Fejer, Magnusson, Christer Sven Milonas, Panagiotis Navas-Cortes, Juan A. Parnell, Stephen Potting, Roel Reig-nault, Philippe Lucien Thulke, Hans-Hermann Van der Werf, Wopke Vicent Civera, Antonio Yuen, Jonathan Zappala, Lucia Malumphy, Chris Czwienczek, Evelina Kertesz, Virag Maiorano, Andrea MacLeod, Alan Efsa Panel Plant Hlth PLH

Attachments
 PDF - EFSA Journal - 2021 - Pest categorisation of *Citripestis sagittiferella*.pdf (Standard Version) | (Annotatable Version)

Full Text Links
 DOI.org

Reference Label(s):
 WoS_Scopus

The EFSA Panel on Plant Health performed a pest categorisation of the citrus pulp borer, *Citripestis sagittiferella* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), for the EU. This oligophagous species, which feeds on *Citrus* spp., occurs in Southeast Asia, mostly in lowlands but can also be found up to 1,200 m above sea level. Adults oviposit on citrus fruit at any stage of the fruit development. Larvae feed in the fruit then abandon it to pupate in the soil within an earthen cocoon. *C. sagittiferella* is multivoltine in its native range. This species is not included in EU Commission Implementing Regulation 2019/2072. Potential entry pathways for *C. sagittiferella*, such as *Citrus* spp. plants for planting with foliage and soil/growing medium, and soil/growing medium by themselves can be considered as closed. The citrus fruit pathway remains open for countries where *C. sagittiferella* is known to occur. Indeed, this species was intercepted several times in the UK during the last decade. Hosts of *C. sagittiferella* are available (*Citrus* spp.) in the southern EU. The EU has climatic conditions that

Submit Form and go to Datarama order or Skip to Next

1. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?
 Yes No Unclear

2. Specify what type of information
 Physiology/Ecology Distribution Others

Figure 1: Title and Abstract Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR, Version 2.35. Evidence Partners; 2021. <https://www.evidencepartners.com/>)

Selecting the answer “yes” meant that the reference was automatically moved to the next level of screening (i.e., full text screening). When it was unclear whether information of interest was available from the title and the abstract the answer “unclear” was selected, automatically carrying the paper on to the next step. The second step of the screening (Figure 2) was based on the full text of the documents previously selected.

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Submit Form and go to Datarama order or Skip to Next

1. INHERITED FROM TIAB SCREENING
 Selection criteria in tiab
 Physiology/Ecology
 Distribution
 Others

2. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?
 Yes No Unclear (to be consulted)

3. What type of information
 Physiology/Ecology
 Distribution
 Other

Figure 2: Full-text Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR, Version 2.35. Evidence Partners; 2021. <https://www.evidencepartners.com/>)

Data extraction

Data extraction was performed on two files for the documents passing the full-text screening. One Excel sheet describing all the relevant extracted information, hereafter referred to as Master file (ANNEX A), and one other csv file was used to record data on pest distribution (ANNEX B).

Table 4: Information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file

Field name	Description	Type
RefID	Record ID. The RefID number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
Reference	Full reference for the record	String
Primary_source	Source of information	String
Physiology_Ecology	Presence of information on physiology and/or ecology (indicated by "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Distribution	Presence of information on distribution (indicated by "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Other	Presence of additional information that could be of interest. Empty means no information	Boolean
T	Presence of information on temperature (indicated by "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
RH	Presence of information on relative humidity or moisture (indicated by "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Photoperiod	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean

Table 4 shows the information extracted from the documents and collected in the Master file, while the distribution file (Table 5) contains data on the georeferenced observations of the pest. To further detail the analysis, an effort was made to categorize, when possible, the observations based on the organism status. Hence, two classifications for the pest status were created. The first one (Species_status1) based on the reported harmfulness of the organism (i.e., Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear), the second (Species_status2) based on the reported persistence of the organism in the observed location (i.e., Persistent, Transient, or Unclear). An additional table associated to the distribution table and including additional notes and information on specific records was also created as a supporting material.

Table 5: Citripestis sagittiferella observations extracted from the documents and collected in the distribution file.

Field name	Description	Type
Obs_ID	The Obs_ID is a unique number associated to each collected observation	Integer
Continent	Continent where the organism observation was reported	String
Country	Country where the organism observation was reported	String
State	State where the organism observation was reported	String
Observation	Location of the organism observation as reported in literature	String
Admin.level	FAO GAUL Administrative level of the observation ('location' in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
Admin.source	Administrative shapefile layer used to identify the area of the organism observation (usually FAO GAUL layer)	String
Admin.code	FAO GAUL Administrative code of the observation ('NA' in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
Lat	Latitude of the organism observation	Double
Long	Longitude of the organism observation	Double
Google_Earth_coord	Indicates if a centroid was used to identify the organism location. Centroids were used only if the observation was not available in the FAO GAUL Administrative subdivision and in case of relatively small entities like towns/cities/provinces. Empty means that the coordinates were already indicated in the literature or that the location is identified by an administrative layer	Boolean
RefID	Record ID. The RefID number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller. This is the same field used also in Table 4.	Integer
Species_status1	Classifies the organism harmfulness in the area of observation (i.e., Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear)	String
Species_status2	Classifies the organism persistence in the area of observation (i.e., Persistent, Transient, or Unclear)	String
Notes	Flagged records (with 'x') include additional information saved in the support table	Boolean
Uncertain	Flagged records (with 'x') refer to documents including uncertain information regarding the organism observation (e.g. records from museums, interceptions, unclear information)	Boolean

Climate Classification analysis

The SCAN-Clim tool (EFSA & Maiorano, 2022) was used to produce climate suitability maps based on the climate classification approach. The approach is based on a Köppen–Geiger climate classification for the period 1986–2010 and on a 0.08° grid from the University of Vienna (Kottek et al., 2006) rescaled after Rubel et al. (2017) (<http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>).

The climate types present in the observed locations of *Citripestis sagittiferella* were identified and mapped. Since the area of the assessment was the EU, the output maps included only climate types that are present in this area. Administrative units where the pest was observed are highlighted with black borders, while point observations are indicated with red dots.

Results

Systematic literature review

Figure 3 summarises the results of the systematic literature search in a PRISMA diagram (Moher et al., 2009). A total of 40 documents were retrieved from the search in scientific databases. Overall, 32 documents were found through the Web of Science platform and 8 through the SCOPUS platform. After excluding duplicates, 39 documents were assessed for the first level screening (title and abstract). Eleven documents were selected for the second level screening (full text). Ten additional references including information on physiology and distribution, found by PhD Krys A.G. Wyckhuys, were also added to the full text screening. A total of 19 papers were used for the data extraction from scientific databases. Out of these 19 papers, 18 included information on *C. sagittiferella* distribution, and 7 information on its ecophysiology.

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

Figure 3: PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Citripestis sagittiferella*.

Observed distribution data

Eighty-seven records of the presence of *C. sagittiferella* were collected, all of them in South-East Asia, specifically in Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and Vietnam. The records are all available in the observation file (ANNEX B), including the uncertainty points excluded from the final maps. Out of these records (Figure 4), 36 are point observations reporting specific coordinates, or small administrative units (e.g., counties) for which coordinates from Google Earth were used. Fifty-one records are related to larger administrative units, like regions or countries. Observations from Obs_ID 2 to Obs_ID 14 were considered uncertain because the identification may have been confused with the species *Mussidia pectinicornella*, according to CABI, DROPSA, and Robinson (1994). Observations Obs_ID 1 and Obs_ID

30 report names of the colonized past of the area, of difficult interpretation today. All uncertain locations were excluded from the final maps.

Figure 4: Observed distribution of *Citripestis sagittiferella*. The map on the left (1) shows point locations (with coordinates) where the pest was reported. The map on the right (2) shows the distribution at the administrative units level.

Climate classification

Due to the little availability of confirmed locations, the climate suitability analysis was limited to the Köppen–Geiger climate matching. No European climate types were recorded under the point observations of the pest, but when larger administrative units are considered, the Cfb climate type is sparsely present in only three units, as shown in Table 6. Thus, the inclusion of the Cfb climate was considered uncertain by the *C. sagittiferella* EFSA PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health et al., 2023) leading to uncertainties in the outcome of the climate suitability analysis.

Table 6: Cfb climate type presence in the observed distribution areas of *Citripestis sagittiferella*.

Observation	Administrative Level (FAO GAUL)	Administrative level total pixel number*	Cfb pixel number*	Percentage of Cfb pixels in the administrative unit(%)
Philippines	0	3504	21	0.60
Sabah	1	865	9	1.04
Jawa Tengah	1	404	4	0.99

(*) considering the 0.08° grid of the Köppen–Geiger map by Kottek et al. (2006) and Rubel et al. (2017)

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